

Metropolitan Cities: Territory and Governability, the Spanish Case

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In the last 50 years, Spain has undergone significant urbanization which created both opportunities and challenges in critical areas such as human settlement, economic growth and particularly governance. The latest wave of urbanization in the Spanish context has not just meant the explosive growth of cities themselves but also of metropolitan regions because of new production and residence patterns, which shaped both processes of population dispersal and recentralization. By focusing on the five principal metropolitan areas in Spain – Madrid, Barcelona, Bilbao, Seville and Valencia – this discussion will explore the transformative impact of recent urbanization on Spanish society: tracing Spanish metropolitan development over the last 50 years; exploring the most recent ‘urban revolution’ and the resulting processes of dispersal and recentralization; and analysing both the factors that threaten the sustainability of some urbanization models and the issues that make governance difficult within the current metropolitan reality. Lastly, we provide innovative strategies for improved management and governance in urban Spain.

Spanish Cities and their Metropolitan Areas

Spanish cities are no exception to the urbanization process that has perpetuated itself all over the world. According to United Nations figures,¹ the world’s urban population has reached 50 per cent around the globe, the European rate being 80 per cent and that of Spain 76 per cent. If we include the population living in highly urbanized areas, the percentages in European countries increase to 90 per cent or more. For the purpose of circumscribing the analysis of Spanish urban reality, we shall centre our study on the five principal Spanish metropolitan areas as regards population. These are the national capital, Madrid; Barcelona (whose metropolitan area is, in surface and popula-

tion, equivalent to Madrid’s), and the three historical capitals of Valencia, on the Mediterranean arc; Bilbao, in the north, the capital of the Basque country, and Seville, the capital of Andalusia in the country’s south. It would be possible to add other cities-metropolitan regions such as Málaga and the urbanized region of the eastern Andalusian coast; the Galician conurbation of Vigo-Pontevedra-Santiago-La Coruña-El Ferrol; or Saragossa (a city-municipality, with an area of 1,2000 km², that is to say six times that of Madrid and 12 times that of Barcelona, which has generated a phenomenon of urban concentration, without a metropolitan region beyond the municipality). We have restricted ourselves to the five main cities because they are also the ones that exhibit features inherent in the metropolitan cities that have developed

in the context of industrial societies, which makes them more comparable with the European and American urban systems.

Nevertheless it is necessary, from the outset, to point out some differences among the five cities and their metropolitan surroundings that must be taken into account when analysing each one's urban processes and making comparisons between them. Their administrative differences may generate statistical confusions. Barcelona and Bilbao are small municipalities (97 and 41 km² respectively), while Madrid's municipality (605.8 km²) includes within its territory the same population that the first two cities contain in their first ring. This means that the pertinent comparison would be, for example, between the municipality of Madrid and the Barcelona agglomeration, the two of which, with similar territories, also bring together similar populations (above 3 million inhabitants). The Bilbao agglomeration, in its 405 km², concentrates one million inhabitants, four times more than the municipality. In addition, the metropolitan region nowadays experiences a conurbanization process that links the three Basque cities, linked by freeways and soon by a high-speed train. Valencia (134 km²) and Seville (141 km²) have until recently been able

to grow within the municipality itself, and with an area larger than Barcelona's have a considerably smaller population. While, surrounded by a region that is populated but has been predominantly rural until a few years ago, these cities have historically been unable to experience the metropolitan process induced by industrial development with the same intensity as have Bilbao, Barcelona and in recent decades Madrid. For this reason we consider it indispensable always to keep in mind the population, the area and the density of the central city or main municipality, of the multi-municipal agglomeration of the first ring (almost always generated by industrial development), and of the metropolitan region (whose articulated development mainly corresponds to the post-industrial urban revolution).

Metropolitan Development and Central Cities over the Last 50 years

The Spanish metropolitan extension has its genesis in the industrialization process, increasing its intensity as of the 1960s, a time when the Spanish economy opened its doors to the international market after decades of autarchy promoted by the existing dictatorial regime. The improvement in job opportunities

Table 1. Population, area and density of Spanish urban regions. (Source: IEMRB, 2004)

	Central City			Urban Agglomeration			Metropolitan Region		
	population	area km ²	density pop/km ²	population	area km ²	density pop/km ²	population	area km ²	density pop/km ²
Barcelona	1,503,883	98	15,346	2,936,563	633	4,639	4,390,390	3,235	1,357
Bilbao	349,972	41	8,536	825,465	405	2,038	1,122,637	2,217	507
Madrid	2,938,723	606	4,849	–	–	–	4,845,083	1,942	2,495
Seville	684,633	141	4,856	–	–	–	1,093,174	579	1,888
Valencia	738,441	135	5,470	1,356,424	493	2,751	1,496,098	950	1,575

Note: the agglomeration corresponds to the central city and the first ring or urban continuum, while the region corresponds to the current strategic and discontinuous urban territory. The agglomeration data for Madrid are not included because after the Civil War it incorporated the peripheral municipalities into the central city. Therefore we can consider that the current municipality is equivalent to the agglomeration constituted by the industrial and demographic development of the middle of the last century. In the case of Seville we consider that agglomeration and metropolitan region are one and the same.

DENSITY

Figure 1. Growth in urban population. (Source: IEMRB, 2004)

in the industrial sector promoted an increase in farm-city migrations, both within the same region and between the country's most depressed areas, where the rural population was predominant, and the above-mentioned large cities. The 1950–1970 mass population influx triggered the disorderly growth that took place in the majority of Spain's large cities without the kinds of social or urban planning or mass public housing programmes being carried out during the same period in other European countries.

Mass transit, and the proximity between the place of production, the factory, and the place of reproduction, the home, underpinned this first metropolitan expansion. It was a dense growth in the shape of an oil stain extending from the central city towards the nearby municipalities and areas. An urbanization that took place on the farmland closest to the metropolis and that, once having fulfilled and saturated the urban centres and plans for expansion of the mid-twentieth century, adopted new forms of city planning that persist today. The most characteristic morphologies of this second urban explosion or revolution² were the housing complexes and the self-build neighbourhoods which are still today in a process of adaptation and improvement of their wretched original conditions.

In referring to the demographic evolution of Spanish cities, figure 1 shows the growth in metropolitan population and in that of the central city between 1960 and 2005. It makes possible the perception of the enormous growth in population both in the central cities and in the metropolitan areas between 1960 and 1975, a strong period of urbanization linked to the industrialization just mentioned. Nevertheless, as of 1975 there was an inflection point. On one hand, the growth in the metropolitan area's total population slowed down in the 1981–1996 period, being almost nil, beginning a new, moderate growth only as of 1996. On the other hand, we can see how the central cities lost population between 1975 and 2001, a trend that was not to vary until the last 5-year period, 2001–2005, when one could see a resurgence in central cities that reached the maximum 1975 population, following the classical models of metropolitan growth (Hall and Hay, 1980; van der Berg, 1982, among others) albeit with nuances. These recentralizing dynamics did not take place in the same way or at the same time in all the cities. Madrid, Barcelona and Bilbao, metropolises of greater maturity and size, lost population in the central city before the other two metropolitan regions, transferring population initially to the first ring and later to the second. Valencia and Seville continued

the same dynamics of metropolitan dispersal delayed a decade. This temporal disjunction between the cities' dynamics balanced out in the last period, 2001–2005, with central-city population recovery in all five cases, thus closing the previously mentioned models: from the initial concentration to suburbanization and dispersal, thence to return to the re-urbanization of the urban centres.

Nevertheless, this population recovery in the central city does not in any of the cases entail a return to the compactness that has historically characterized Spanish cities. On the contrary, rather there simultaneously coexist two apparently divergent dynamics at the present time configuring Spanish cities' urban structure. We are speaking of the processes of dispersal and recentralization.

The Third Urban Revolution: The Processes of Dispersal and Recentralization in Spanish Cities

If the second urban revolution of the mid-twentieth century was characterized by the concentration of production means and of city populations and the compact growth of the metropolitan areas that take advantage of economies of scale and closeness to markets, labour pools and transport infrastructure, the current, third urban revolution is marked by complexity and the proliferation of economic, political and social processes and dynamics. Here we will not give a comprehensive analysis of the structural changes that have promoted this third urban revolution (Borja and Castells, 1997; Borja, 2003, *inter alia*) but will focus on analysing the urban dispersal process that characterizes developments of the last two decades. In a later section we will

analyse the recentralization resulting from more recent processes that are the other face of current metropolitan Spanish realities.

Cities have turned into the economy's nodes not only regionally but also nationally and globally. Proof of this is that Spain's regions' population³ polarized by the five large Spanish cities represent 31.3 per cent of the country's population while the GDP of the five regions represents 44.5 per cent of the total national economy. But beyond the dependence with regard to worldwide economic dynamics and the renewed roles of metropolises in the new global production processes, circulation and consumption, it is the variety of urban agents' territorial demands that induces the growth and diversification of urban functions and morphologies in the metropolitan territory. We must not forget that in a period of weak planning and strong markets it is socio-territorial processes at local and regional levels that ultimately define the metropolitan urban structure. Acting on the assumption that urban agents settle in the various parts of the metropolis according to their needs and opportunities – in the case of individuals to maximize their welfare and in the case of corporations their profits – it is the land and housing markets, and to a lesser extent territorial planning (especially planning that implies constructing large-scale infrastructure), that, as a last resort, determine, filter and in a direct or indirect manner allocate who, and which functions, are located in each part of the metropolitan territory.

For the purpose of exemplifying in a quantitative manner the dispersal process in Spanish cities, table 2 shows us the Metropolitan Region of Madrid (MRM)'s absolute growth of population and urbanized land. It

Table 2. Population and urbanized land in the Metropolitan Region of Madrid. (*Source*: Naredo in Borja and Muxí, 2004)

	1957	1980	1999
Population	2,307,000	4,431,000	4,711,000
Urbanized area (km ²)	10,700	35,100	49,000

reveals the high pace of urbanization in the last 50 years. In the entire period analysed, 1957–1999, the population doubled, growing from 2,307,000 to 4,711,000 inhabitants, while the urbanized area has quintupled, increasing from 10,700 to 49,000 hectares.

If we note the relationship between the urbanized area per 1,000 inhabitants we shall see urbanization's pace intensifying in the last period, 1980–1999; while between 1957 and 1980, 11.5 hectares were urbanized for each 1,000 new inhabitants, in the last 20 years the corresponding urbanized area has been 50 hectares. This excessive urban land consumption induces us to perceive a change in the residential and production model. Thus, while the city's explosive growth, by virtue of industrialization, in the second urban revolution, produced a relatively compact urban fabric, in the last 20 years the pace of urbanization has risen, in relation, as we shall see below, with new production and residence patterns based on a real estate boom and extremely permissive planning.

To make the evidence of the phenomenon of urban dispersal clearer we shall zero in on the growth of the diverse metropolitan rings around Barcelona, presented in table 3. Between 1972 and 1999 the second metropolitan ring, with more than 300 per cent, has seen its urbanized surface increase the most, more than triple the first ring and six times more than the central city. It shows that we are speaking of an urban dispersal at a metropolitan scale in which the central city sees its territorial growth restricted in favour of the first and above all of the second metropolitan ring. In total, the urbanized area

of the Barcelona metropolitan region has doubled in the last 25 years while its total population has remained stable!

It should be noted that this process of dispersal adopts different forms and sizes according to the city. Barcelona and Bilbao are seeing their polycentric urban structure blur by virtue of low-density territorial dispersion and spread. Although the most important urban nodes are preserved, the spreading stain gradually takes over the metropolitan territory adopting forms more reminiscent of the *città diffusa* of Italy's Central Veneto or Emilia Romagna than of their original structure.

Madrid, Seville and Valencia, with urban structures highly polarized by the central city, see urban dispersal widening the metropolitan region but not diversifying it functionally. Daily mobility continues to be mono-directional, from the periphery downtown and vice versa, increasing the use of private vehicles and of the road infrastructure.

Factors at the Root of Some Minimally Sustainable Urbanization Models

Having presented the data, we shall attempt to point out the causes that have promoted an urbanization process that has high social, environmental and functional costs, unprecedented in Spanish cities' urbanization process. We are referring, thus, to the change from a structure that is compact and based on proximity to an urban dispersal derived from using the entire metropolitan territory as a single functional unit, be it for residential or for manufacturing purposes.

Table 3. Urbanized land (hectares) in the Metropolitan Region of Barcelona.
(Source: Herce in Borja and Muxí, 2004)

	1972	1986	1992	1999	Percentage change 1972–1999
Barcelona	4,244	5,708	6,040	6,166	45.29
First ring	5,316	9,979	11,430	12,386	132.99
Second ring	7,431	22,723	26,929	30,020	303.98

In the first place it should be stressed that the urban dispersal process is a consequence of its being facilitated by the agents – public or private – configuring the metropolitan territory. The lack of any comprehensive planning for the entire metropolitan area – in none of the cities is there a specific administrative body of a comprehensive nature – has promoted a lack of coordination and even competition at the municipal level to accommodate the maximum possible number of taxpayers. On the other hand, the lack of awareness of urban dispersal's costs has given total immunity to the most atrocious territorial plundering, irreversibly destroying natural assets.

Secondly, we find changes in the economic structure. The crisis in the Fordian model that led to agglomeration in large cities, and the consequent implantation of a fragmented production system that is specialized and structured as a network, has entailed the decentralization and dispersal of the productive fabric.

Thirdly, the democratization of the private vehicle and its use as an everyday form of transport, accompanied by improved accessibility because of better road infrastructure to the detriment of railways, has triggered changes in functions and relations in the metropolitan region. The price differences between the central city and existing urban nodes on one hand, and the rest of the metropolitan territory on the other, have decisively promoted dispersal.

Fourthly, these dispersing and segregating dynamics have been reinforced by public policies favouring road infrastructure and in so doing have promoted increasing urban surplus value in peripheral areas, stimulating the urbanization of land distant from the continuous urban fabric. This has multiplied cases of corruption among local and area authorities, both in metropolitan and in tourist areas, which have awarded legally dubious building permits or have arbitrarily changed zoning to open rural land to urbanization. In small or medium-

sized periphery municipalities or in tourist areas, developers and construction firms have directly organized mayoral candidacies and in a good number of cases have personally filled the mayoralties.

The fifth determining factor has been the diversification of the urban residential supply and the consolidation of 'universal' lifestyles that traditionally had minimal presence in Spain. In the case of Barcelona, during the 1987–2001 period, a third of the new housing built has been one-family units, their existence most intense in the smaller municipalities of the second metropolitan ring (Muñoz, 2005). We refer to the marketing of residential typologies such as free-standing or semi-detached houses, facilitated both by intensive car usage and by the dispersal of places of employment.

The sixth factor accentuating urbanization and, consequently, urban dispersal, relates to the change in the financial system and in the world economic situation which has promoted the real estate and construction business as one of the most profitable activities in Spain since the mid-1990s. Low interest rates and the facility to obtain loans in the mortgage market have prompted a construction boom and turned housing purchases (or offices, parking lots, etc.) into a form of saving for the middle and even the popular classes.

In table 4 we can see the increase in the Gross Added Value of the construction sector between the years 2000 and 2003 and its high relative weight *vis-à-vis* the total provincial

Table 4. Percentage of the Gross Added Value of the construction sector with regard to the province's GDP. (Source: INE)

	2000	2003
Seville	6.37	8.11
Barcelona	5.37	6.69
Valencia	7.90	8.42
Madrid	6.64	7.99
Valencia	7.41	8.80

Figure 2. Foreign populations influx into Spanish cities by year.

GDP, an unequivocal sign of construction's importance as a pillar of urban economies.

And lastly, the appearance of a 'recentralization' (see the next section), a dynamic of contradictory tendencies, has not replaced the dynamic of dispersal, which is maintained and conquers new territories at ever greater distances from both downtown and the most densely populated areas. This indicates that the factors at work are structural in nature.

The Recentralization Process

While the urban dispersal process is based on the urbanization of the metropolitan territory, the recentralization process is more closely related to the phenomena of rehabilitation and revaluation and, consequently, with the degeneration and devaluation of urban centres. The new economic activities with a high added value related either to the knowledge economy or to the outsourcing of excellence, seek to base themselves in the central city in order to maximize their profits. Some of the motivations for recentralization include the need constantly to establish face-to-face relationships and have access to services of excellence. The renewed interest in central city improvement and rehabilitation by part of the administration and the private sector has highlighted competition among cities to attract financial, human and cultural capital, in addition to tourists. The adaptation of productive spaces and of existing housing as well as 'city marketing' campaigns to boost

the city's international image are some of the results of this process.⁴ With regard to the change in the residential structure we point out the processes of (relative) gentrification of cities' historic neighbourhoods – Barrio Gótico and Borne in Barcelona, Chueca in Madrid, Santa Cruz in Seville or Carmen in Valencia – as a consequence of this central city internationalization with arrivals of tourists and temporary visitors as the main catalysts for this situation.

Although the central city's rehabilitation and its renewed functional and symbolic interest result from a formal strategy, there are also other factors of an informal nature that promote the urban recentralization process. The arrival of a new wave of immigrants coming from developing countries is another determining factor that explains recentralization, although in this case it is the source of some central city neighbourhoods' degradation as well as over-occupied housing.

If we look at figure 2, we note the foreign population's high entry rate which, at the national level, already represents 10 per cent of the total Spanish population. No detailed analysis is required to notice that more than 40 per cent of foreigners arrived between 1997 and 2001, and only around 10 per cent resided in Spain before 1980. Therefore we are talking about a high influx of population which, as already took place in the twentieth century, initially resides (to a great extent) in degraded downtown areas or aging,

traditional neighbourhoods in the main cities in order to find job opportunities as much as to seek security and assistance from fellow countrymen already settled there.

Thus, the recentralization process in Spanish cities has opposing social and economic agents and processes. On the one hand, the direct or indirect attraction of a more or less skilled population that bases its way of life on the urban supply and, on the other, an impoverished immigrant population that finds itself forced to crowd together in the city in search of security and opportunities to improve its quality of life. These are two social processes which are cause and effect of a dual urban process: the rehabilitation and degradation of the central city.

The Issue of the Difficult Governability of Metropolitan Cities

The urban-metropolitan territorial complexity generates a range of difficulties, both for analysis and for developing and implementing public policies. We have already referred to the difficulty in comparing cities because of the diversity that exists among administrative areas, which are containers of important information (on demographics, city planning, socio-economics, etc.), particularly data of a statistical character. It is even difficult to establish new territorial borders because the metropolitan parameters vary geographically. Traditional indicators (like those relating to territorial continuity, daily mobility and the existence of services in common) serve to delimit the agglomerations constituted over the course of decades of industrial society. They are the classical metropolitan areas, in many cases defined since the 1950s or 1960s, in which the most pertinent relationship is that between centre and periphery. Nevertheless these indicators are insufficient to define the discontinuous metropolitan regions, with areas that are highly integrated ('globalized') and others that are marginal or secluded, and with erratic mobilities and multi-polarities.

Not only that, but the administration or governability of this territorial complexity is even more difficult. In some cases there exists an institution that is relatively well suited to the metropolitan regional scope, as in the case of Madrid and its autonomous community which has jurisdiction over territorial and socio-economic matters that is relatively effective for new and old public policies, referring to both social production and reproduction. In other cases the institutional sphere exists but the type of organization that embodies it, by historical and administrative tradition, political composition and set of responsibilities and resources, is not suited to developing metropolitan policies. This is the situation that the other afore-mentioned Spanish provinces face.

In all cases, the constitutional framework guarantees the autonomy of municipalities while their competitive parallel operations generate dysfunctions because there does not exist in Spain (or, in general, in Europe) either legal regulations or any tradition of inter-institutional cooperation based on contractualization; rather the principles of compartmentalization of authority and of hierarchy among institutions persist and prevail.

And yet the governability of metropolitan regions is today a key issue both for cities and countries, because of the importance of these cities in overall political, economic and cultural life. It is impossible to extrapolate the institutional or administrative forms of the old metropolitan areas (the agglomeration pertaining to the industrial city) to the current metropolitan regions. In the first place, for the simple reason that it is a problem that has not been solved in the past and that in general has only given rise to the proliferation of sectorial policies that depend on distinct authorities, public or mixed entities or concessions to private companies to run programmes or services of a metropolitan nature. And the second reason is that the metropolitan region is a reality on a much larger scale, subjected to the challenges of

globalization and requiring an authority and resources that go beyond those that have pertained to municipalities, since they must respond to the issues posed not only by social reproduction at a larger scale than in the past (housing, education, social and cultural programmes) but also to those of social production (vast infrastructural works, attraction and regulation of economic activities, policies aimed at guaranteeing social cohesiveness and environmental sustainability, etc.) The authority required is not only implicit in municipalities, but also affects the financial and jurisdictional scope of both autonomous communities and the state. Therefore what is needed is a metropolitan institutionality that represents the total population and all municipalities and that also enables coordination between the local and supra-municipal level and the 'autonomous' and federal levels. Without this, it will not be possible to develop comprehensive and strategic policies, including those that organize and manage: the territory; social redistribution and cultural integration; attracting investment-generating activities and employment; and optimizing and promoting the sustainability of basic resource usage (land, energy, water, air).

On the basis of the Spanish experience, we lastly point out the main difficulties that appear when it comes to setting up metropolitan political structures endowed with representation and effective authority. One significant fact: in Spain, during the dictatorship, between 1960 and 1970, metropolitan entities were established. Firstly, Barcelona's metropolitan entity initially had a 'technical' character (1960), with central government and capital city representatives, but without peripheral municipalities. Between 1974 and 1976, the Metropolitan Corporation was created, with authority to undertake major city planning, leaving the surrounding municipalities with only a minority role. The autonomous government of Catalonia, chosen in 1980 and already under a democratic government, suppressed the

Corporation in 1987. The embryonic metropolitan entities set up in Madrid, Bilbao, Valencia and Seville met the same fate, whether they were inherited from the previous regime or had been created or reformed within the new, democratic framework. The metropolitan entities were not well received by either the governments of the autonomous communities (equivalent to the German *Länder*, the Italian regions or the states in countries with a federal structure) or, in general, by the peripheral municipalities. The autonomous governments were suspicious of a metropolitan area controlled by political institutions, perceived as 'counter-powers' with the same kind of power that the Constitution had given to the Autonomous Communities. In some cases they might represent half or more of the population (Barcelona and Bilbao); in others, like the Madrid case, their territory was virtually coterminous with that of the Autonomous Community.

The recently elected municipal governments on the periphery, for their part, resisted accepting that local authority should be in the hands of an entity they regarded as dominated by the central city, and feared that because of the latter's power, unwanted projects would be imposed on them. In other words, the suppression of the metropolitan entities did not arouse major opposition. Even the governing parties in the central city, which publicly defended continuing and reinforcing the metropolitan areas, found advantages in that suppression. In the first place, those same parties also filled peripheral mayoralties, and therefore in them all the existing powerful lobbies that expressed the previously mentioned resistance. Moreover, the replacement of the metropolitan entities by specialized agencies, utilities or bureaux (dedicated to the environment, transport, economic promotion, etc.) multiplied the posts and sinecures to distribute among political representatives.

The federal government, for its part, which had to share territorial authority with

the autonomous governments, also was not particularly interested in having another powerful interlocutor that would demand participation in governmental undertakings (for example large road infrastructure works, ports, airports, etc.) and above all, access to resources to cover capital costs. The results have been, at least in appearance, quite chaotic. The federal government and the autonomous governments design and execute infrastructure projects, administer these types of services and establish city planning rules that determine the character of housing, the environment, transport and mobility, etc. But local governments establish the urban plans (which the autonomous government must approve, but not draw up) and manage services and programmes that provide housing, the environment, transport, etc. Since in many cases what are involved are activities and roles that affect more than one municipality, there is a multiplication of *ad hoc* entities, consortia, governmental or mixed corporations, etc.

And to complicate the situation even further, the provinces remain as local entities and delegations of the autonomous and federal governments, just like the French *département* or the British counties, and corresponding to the pre-constitutional, centralist or unitary state model. Which is to say, that although the scope of the territory could adapt, relatively well, to the new metropolitan realities, the provinces' composition, jurisdiction and image do not appear suited to the metropolitan challenges.

The provinces impinge on the territory: local road networks, social and cultural programmes, assistance to the small and medium-sized municipalities, etc. In some cases the province has in fact disappeared (Madrid, since it is a uni-provincial autonomous community) and in others it has little weight in metropolitan territorial politics (Barcelona, because of the expansive power of the capital city and the existence of diverse specialized metropolitan entities). In other

cases, however, it exerts major influence whether because of its economic potential (in the Basque country it is the province that collects taxes), or because of the territorial size and the relative distance of the 'regional' capital (in the case of Andalusia the capital, Seville, has strong centrality in the western area, but not in the eastern, which is further away and in which Málaga and its coastal conurbation are predominant). As if the inherited situation was not sufficient, some autonomous governments have created their own supra-municipal division, with the name of *comarca* (region) or an equivalent, either to promote the joint operation of local roles and services among several municipalities, or to bring together the local interlocutors with whom to reach consensus on plans or programmes, or to cooperate in service management.

The result is not always negative, since the situation offers diverse possibilities and therefore an institutional flexibility that breaks the traditional rigidity of the states' political organization, based on the *droit administratif* model of Napoleonic origin. This favours local initiatives and makes possible adapting *ad hoc* to diverse problems and circumstances. Nevertheless the drawbacks of this confusing complexity are evident. The most important, in our view, are the following:

1. The *opacity* of institutional operations and of public policies. In many cases responsibilities are diluted; in others, one does not know very clearly who makes decisions. In general, the citizenry neither clearly understands the realities of the realm in which it necessarily acts nor that it is affected by public policies (by action or omission), and this therefore contributes to the creation of passive or impotent citizens. The formal institutionalization of the metropolitan reality is essential for the citizenry to feel part of it.
2. The non-existence of a *future scenario* or of an *overall or general plan*. These would not only guide and give coherence to metro-

politan policies, but also provide assurances and participatory mechanisms for public and private actors and further debate with citizen, professional, university and cultural groups.

3. The *proliferation of organizations*, specialized but in some cases not very representative, in others with political representation but insufficient authority and resources, not only leads to overlapping, confrontations and inflationary costs, but also favours collusion between particular public and private interests.

4. *Competition among these entities, especially among municipalities*, can lead to forms of local dumping (i.e. offering the municipality cheaply to investors), to the exclusion of what does not seem profitable or attractive (social housing, immigration, unwanted infrastructure), and to the development of a 'not in my own back yard' culture.

5. The result of all the above is the *relative impotence of metropolitan policies* with regard to market dynamics and to the sectorial decisions of the federal government and of large corporations.

Metropolitan governability was not solved in the territories produced by industrial society's development. This means that the metropolitan realities are linked to a central city (or in some cases conurbations of two or more cities, each with its own measure of centrality) and to the integration of the peripheries according to patterns of continuous territorial occupation. In the new post-industrial society there emerged a third dimension of the metropolitan phenomenon, the region, for simplicity's sake. Although a principal centrality may exist, there also exists a diversity of centralities. The metropolitan regional territory offers differentiated degrees of occupation and areas of high density coexist with others of low or no urbanization (rural areas, protection zones, etc.) It is

difficult to assign the governability of this new territory to a new, specific institution.

In the annex that follows we raise various possibilities for political administration that is beginning to be tested in these metropolitan regions. Because of its formal and general character, we consider it more appropriate to consider it as a complementary text rather than as a section within the article.

ANNEX on Metropolitan Cities and Governability⁵

The New Metropolitan Reality

It is necessary to distinguish, at least in theory, between an agglomeration (the classical metropolitan area, the central city and its immediate periphery, the urban continuum, the area of daily moves) and a metropolitan region (discontinuous, strategic and polycentric).

Without seeking to rule on the roles corresponding to the two theoretical levels set forth, we mention some criteria derived from cases studied and from a certain managerial logic:

First level (strictu sensu agglomeration): what prevail are common services (water, transport, police...) and immediate and medium-scale social and urban development projects (housing, urban renewal, recycling of obsolete areas, etc.). It is an area of supra-municipal, not only inter-municipal local administration.

Second level (the metropolitan region): an area of more strategic than regulatory planning, which must operate according to a variable geometry but that also requires a stable, cooperative area of operations. Priority must be assigned to large metropolitan projects, mainly of an infrastructural nature, 'consistency setups' or plans for basic systems, and rules aimed at guaranteeing that the urban development is balanced.

In either case, programmes and projects

must find the appropriate territorial scale, be they urban projects and social programmes, in which the level of 'agglomeration' will have primacy, or infrastructural and economic development plans and projects, more attuned to the urban region. The agglomeration level requires planning and management, a common fiscal base, redistributive and rebalancing policies, and a representative political organization (elected directly or indirectly and with the presence of all the municipalities). The regional level can be based on a regional strategic plan shared with the federal government; it must be of variable geometry and can be carried out by means of a catalogue of programmes and projects and the coordination of the investments of the coordinated entities, which can be diverse (federal and municipal governments, provincial councils or the equivalent and metropolitan entities, consortia, etc.) The level of agglomeration or small metropolitan area can be consolidated by means of a political and cultural process with a *sui generis* strategic plan more centred on quality of life, social cohesiveness, sustainability, the development of a diversity of centralities and democratic governability than by competitiveness and major infrastructure projects. Large-scale infrastructure, if it is not yet carried out or programmed, should be integrated with regional or large-scale strategic planning.

Governability

This new metropolitan reality, of varying sizes, does not allow one sole solution. Nevertheless the articulation of public policies renders it necessary to define a concrete 'territory'. The territory 'experienced' is not the 'strategic' territory. A representative political structuring, with the capacity to develop comprehensive and redistributive public policies, probably should be based more on the present experienced territory than on the strategic future ones. The political challenge is that of erecting democratic

structures that correspond to these new territories.

Agglomeration: it is necessary to find formulae for a strong representative democracy, complemented by multiple forms of deliberative and participative democracy.

Metropolitan region: it must round out the mechanisms of coordination and inter-institutional contractualization pertaining to the 'large-scale' or strategic metropolitan sphere with original and in many cases *ad hoc* participative mechanisms (for specific major projects or particular campaigns), and in other cases stable ones, like the development councils under French law.

Promoting this planning and management process requires specific governmental or mixed entities. The level of the *agglomeration* or traditional *metropolitan area* surely needs a representative political entity, based on directly elected municipal governments or councils, with the authority to handle common services and with redistributive goals. The *regional* level, on the other hand, entails the creation of a collaborative framework among governmental institutions of different levels, specific and diversified mechanisms of public-private cooperation and participation, and agencies to operate strategic projects or programmes. For example:

Metropolitan Council of Agglomeration: A local political entity formed by the government of the central city (city and delegations or districts) and by the metropolitan mayoralities. It takes on the authority for urban planning and for management of urban services, on the basis of a sustainable development plan that promotes social integration. It handles the problems, social, cultural and economic services agreed upon by the municipalities.

Metropolitan Regional Consortium: If it exists and constitutes an appropriate arena, it can

replace or be taken over by the department or province. Also, a council composed of representatives of the metropolitan region's local entities can be created *ad hoc*, with potential participation of representatives of regional or federal institutions. It would be in charge of drawing up a strategic plan and designing one or several consortia or agencies with economic, social, professional cultural and university institutions and organizations, charged with managing the former, with a coordinating role *vis-à-vis* the institutions' investment plans and following up on the programmes and projects adopted.

The federal government should have the capacity to draw up its own proposals, concrete and transversal, based on values and goals that achieve wide consensus and legitimacy, in its relations with the regions, the metropolitan areas or the agglomerations. In the case of the biggest and most discontinuous and polycentric metropolitan urban areas, it seems reasonable to establish a diversity of contracts between the federal government and the territorial entities on the basis of a common trunk agreed on with the region or with the agglomeration, according to case.

The contractualized metropolitan policies must – precisely because of their ambition, the fact that diverse populations' resources and objectives are invested in them, and because the many partners involved can lead to a certain blurring of responsibilities – be the object of rigorous monitoring and periodic evaluation.

The federal government should see in these processes of comprehensive planning and of contractualized programming an opportunity to reform its services, making them nimble and more operative, more akin to boosting and providing technical support than to direct management or bureaucratic oversight, more transversal than sectorial; in sum, connected politically with the territory but without attempting to take it over administratively.

NOTES

1. See report of the UN World Urbanization Prospect (2003) <http://www.un.org/esa/population/publications/wup2003/2003WUPHighlights.pdf>
2. See Ascher, F. (2001).
3. As statistical basis we employ the scope of the provinces, the Spanish equivalent of the French *départements* or the Anglo-Saxon counties, which correspond approximately to the current metropolitan region.
4. The case of Bilbao is the paradigmatic case because of its international implications.
5. The nature of this point is that of a suggestion and is based on the political and professional experience of Jordi Borja, who in the 1980s was executive director of the Barcelona metropolitan area and later worked as consultant on these issues in diverse European and Latin American countries (France, Italy, Argentina, Mexico, Brazil, etc.).

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